

Theoretical Aspects of Organization of Homework from Reading Lessons in Primary Class

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Abstract

This article is based on the theoretical aspects of homework organization from primary school reading lessons, the scientific and methodological study of homework organization as a social necessity. The content and specifics of homework from reading lessons in primary class are analyzed in detail. The article provides recommendations for students to start independent activities based on homework in primary classes.

Keywords: Primary education, homework, education, learning, collaboration, effective outcome, person-centered learning, assignment, independent thinking, question-assignment, activity, systematic approach, text, logical thinking, individual approach,

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The basis of primary education is the idea of personal development, its harmonious formation and development. In this regard, the proposed system of views and ideas represents the prospects for primary education based on traditional teaching, integrated, person-centered and based on a competency-based approach.

In the educational process, traditional teaching is being replaced by person-centered approaches. In this regard, regular monitoring of students' knowledge, skills and abilities, timely filling in gaps in students' knowledge, to create conditions for the continuous development of intellectual potential in gifted students, to encourage them to work with adults, enrichment of pedagogical approaches and practices aimed at protecting and strengthening their health, development of a plan of extracurricular pedagogical activities, regular use of modern pedagogical technologies and advanced achievements of pedagogical science in the educational process, i.e. the introduction of elements of information and communication technologies in the educational process, to use them effectively, to establish cooperation of teachers with parents, tasks such as the use of modern methods in the retraining and continuous professional development of primary school teachers remain relevant [3.4].

In the Concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, developed in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 emphasized “although state education standards are based on a competency-based approach, teaching and assessment methods, as well as textbooks and other teaching materials, focus on memorizing and describing information, critical thinking, independent information retrieval and analysis skills, and hinders the development of other skills”.

The concept states that homework is important in solving existing problems in the field of public education, organizing independent activities of students, developing logical thinking, teaching critical thinking. This underscores the importance of improving an innovative approach to the organization of homework from reading lessons in the formation of independent thinking skills in students.

However, there is a need to clarify the methodological aspects of homework organization in primary class. The level of independence of thinking and activity, which is the basis of the spiritual development of the student, is also reflected in the performance of homework. The most important condition for homework is that the lessons and the facts in the textbook should not be repeated.

Students' homework is closely linked to their homework. The success of the homework depends on how well the lesson went and how well the teacher did the homework. Therefore, the higher the quality of the lesson, the more successful and effective the students' homework will be [4.21].

The success of students' homework depends in large part on the quality of their work. It is important for the teacher to understand that students will not be able to complete the task if they do not know how to do it. For this reason, instructions should be provided for each assignment, which may include:

- ✓ demonstrate a simple way to complete a task in the same way as before;
- ✓ explain the task on the basis of two or three examples;

- ✓ discuss the most important aspects of homework in class;
- ✓ explain the requirements for the work and methods of performance of tasks;

It is important to keep in mind that the younger the students, the clearer and more detailed the guidance will be. It is important for primary class students to specify the order of assignments:

- 1) memorize the rule on page 15;
- 2) complete Exercises 3 to 4 on page 16.

When this is done, students first write down an assignment to master the rule and then complete the exercise. The teacher decides when to give homework, depending on the purpose and structure of the lesson. Typically, throughout the lesson, children are given a task prepared to consciously comprehend the task. [4.34]. It is important to keep in mind that assignments are given in a relaxed, relaxed atmosphere when students are fully engaged. Each assignment must be reviewed by the teacher in one form or another. It is a good idea for the teacher to be able to check all the students and make the test as accurate as possible so that there are no mistakes in the students' work. It is important to get students used to doing homework every day. This requires a system of work to be done. Students will be required to:

- ✓ provide them with thorough guidance and training to work independently;
- ✓ to develop a thorough system of control over their work;
- ✓ strict adherence to the student's schedule, with time for homework;
- ✓ students should be taught to solve problems independently. It should be noted that the description and methodology of homework in many respects depends on the method of work of the teacher in the classroom.

To increase the independent and creative activity of students in the educational process in the face of primary education, there are a number of tasks such as to awaken their inner need for independent acquisition of knowledge, to expand their worldview, to ensure their participation in the path of spiritual maturity. In this sense, it is important to organize the educational process in such a way as to ensure that the student consciously acquires knowledge, enters into the essence of the topic or task under study, and acquires independent thinking and working methods [4.47].

Given that homework helps students to develop intelligence and freedom in their personalities, when homework is assigned in reading lessons, the student's attention is first drawn and thought-provoking. The task then emphasizes the need to identify the causes of an event or incident, explain it, draw conclusions, and substantiate one's views. Guides students to think, analyze, respond, and draw conclusions based on examples. In Grade 3-4 reading, "How do you explain this situation in the text?", "Find out why. Justify your views", "How do you feel about this situation? How do you prove your point?", "How do you feel about the hero's actions?" Think about the reasons for this effect, think about the reasons for the incentive (or punishment) given to the hero's activities.

Even in the process of asking for homework, teachers do not use additional questions that encourage the student to think, to express personal attitudes, they cannot have an experience that demonstrates thinking, but to allow students to develop qualities such as initiative, awareness and ingenuity, independent. Students are not always able to solve their homework in a positive way. This is due not only to his abilities, but also to his interest in the task [5.388].

A student who is tasked with separating important aspects from the content of a topic studied as homework by the teacher will be left alone with the homework. If the direction is given correctly, the task will be performed correctly. To do this, the student should:

- first determines the subject of the thought;
- divides the text into important and secondary logical parts;
- finds keywords and concepts;
- identifies the main points for expressing the brief essence of the text and based on them distinguishes its important aspects;
- makes a small plan of the text.

The student is prepared to present his / her views orally or in writing based on the plan.

Effective organization of lessons in school can relatively reduce the amount of homework. But that doesn't mean giving up homework. It is not a good idea not to give students homework. It is known that students have different levels of memory and knowledge. One has the ability to hear and the other has the ability to remember what they have seen. Some students feel the need to read the material from the book after the teacher's statement and memorize its main points [5.345].

The didactic requirements for homework for students in grades 1-4 of primary education do not differ much. Homework assignments at each stage of the primary education process are based on the following recommendations:

- student mastery;
- clarity of its purpose, tasks and order of execution;
- how the homework is related to the topics covered in the new and previous lessons;
- not repeating the classroom material exactly;
- be a complementary and developmental part of a previously studied topic;
- it is advisable to take into account the completion of tasks within the specified time interval.

In our opinion, the teacher's skill is to be able to choose homework for each stage of the lesson, appropriate to a particular situation. In primary school, there are certain ways in which students organize homework. Including:

- homework assignments;
- tasks to work on the text of the work;
- homework for memorization;
- photo assignments;

- tasks for working with questions and assignments;
- keyword assignments;
- homework assignments for students.

The homework assignments in this area help the teacher to organize the students' homework, to manage them in a certain system and to set the controls correctly.

When primary class teachers approach homework assignments based on the suggestions and recommendations outlined above, important tasks such as developing students' knowledge, skills, competencies, and competencies in relation to the topic covered will be accomplished.

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